

Supplemental Materials

Planning-Oriented Suitability Assessment of Passenger Vertiport Candidate Sites: Ground-Based and Rooftop Screening in Jianye, Nanjing

This supplemental file provides auxiliary materials for the AHP-based weighting process and detailed scenario-level sensitivity analysis results. Consistency test results and sensitivity-analysis scenario definitions are reported in the main manuscript.

Table S1. Group judgment matrices for AHP-based weighting

Expert pairwise comparisons were synthesized using the geometric mean method. Weight vectors are reported below each panel.

Panel A. Group judgment matrix for first-level indicators

Indicator order: site buildability (A1), transport and locational conditions (A2), and safety-related constraints (A3).

Indicator	A1	A2	A3
A1 Site buildability	1.000	0.654	1.524
A2 Transport and locational conditions	1.529	1.000	2.330
A3 Safety-related constraints	0.656	0.429	1.000

Weight vector: $W = (0.314, 0.480, 0.206)$.

Panel B. Group judgment matrix for site buildability indicators

Indicator order: spatial-scale indicator (B1) and building-carrier suitability (B2). For rooftop candidate sites, B1 refers to rooftop area and B2 refers to building-carrier suitability. For ground-based candidate sites, site buildability is represented by ground-site scale, while rooftop-specific indicators are excluded and the remaining applicable weights are renormalized in the main manuscript.

Indicator	B1	B2
B1 Spatial-scale indicator	1.000	1.740
B2 Building-carrier suitability	0.575	1.000

Weight vector: $W = (0.635, 0.365)$.

Panel C. Group judgment matrix for indicators under transport and locational conditions

Indicator order: metro accessibility (C1), population density (C2), and functional-zone matching (C3).

Indicator	C1	C2	C3
C1 Metro accessibility	1.000	2.446	1.680
C2 Population density	0.409	1.000	0.687
C3 Functional-zone matching	0.595	1.456	1.000

Weight vector: $W = (0.499, 0.204, 0.297)$.

Panel D. Group judgment matrix for indicators under safety-related constraints

Indicator order: distance to high-risk facilities (D1) and distance to noise-sensitive receptors (D2).

Indicator	D1	D2
D1 Distance to high-risk facilities	1.000	1.513
D2 Distance to noise-sensitive receptors	0.661	1.000

Weight vector: $W = (0.602, 0.398)$.

Table S2. Detailed scenario-level sensitivity analysis results for rooftop and ground-based candidate sites

The area change rate is calculated relative to the baseline area of the relative high-suitability class. A spatial overlap rate closer to 1 indicates greater consistency with the baseline scenario.

Candidate-site type	Scenario	Relative high-suitability candidate sites	Relative high-suitability area (km ²)	Area change rate (%)	Spatial overlap rate
Rooftop candidate sites	Baseline	387	1.259	—	1.000
	W1+	196	0.855	-32.11	0.666
	W1-	229	0.930	-26.18	0.725
	W2+	212	0.891	-29.26	0.694
	W2-	201	0.898	-28.68	0.700
	W3+	217	0.952	-24.43	0.742
	W3-	204	0.858	-31.90	0.668
	T1+	387	1.275	1.28	1.000
	T1-	388	1.276	1.30	1.000
	T2+	407	1.332	5.77	1.000
	T2-	358	1.195	-5.11	0.949
	T3+	401	1.298	3.05	1.000
	T3-	369	1.255	-0.35	0.983
Ground-based candidate sites	Baseline	22	0.322	—	1.000
	W1+	23	0.328	1.74	1.000
	W1-	21	0.311	-3.46	0.963
	W2+	21	0.311	-3.46	0.963
	W2-	24	0.332	3.10	1.000
	W3+	23	0.323	0.23	1.000
	W3-	21	0.316	-1.95	0.963
	T1+	22	0.322	0.00	1.000
	T1-	22	0.322	0.00	1.000
	T2+	21	0.311	-3.46	0.963
	T2-	21	0.319	-0.93	0.991
	T3+	23	0.342	6.35	1.000
	T3-	22	0.322	0.00	1.000